

INVESTIGATION OF MANUFACTURING PERFORMANCE EFFECT ON SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Manufacturing success depends on a well-managed supply chain since it may dramatically lower operational costs and boost profitability for a company. Supply chain management include distribution, production, and logistics. Each stage of the process, starting from generating ideas to promoting the final product, clearly displays its effectiveness. This study analyzed and assessed the risk variables associated with supply chain management to identify the specific dangers that affect this industry. Five categories were established based on the hazards that were identified. One sub-factor examines the underlying causes of the hazards linked with these variables. The surveys and the model underwent the MCDM approach to determine the most critical component in each group. The evaluation of hazards associated with managing the supply chain in Iraq was conducted using questionnaires and expert interviews. The specialists deemed the risk prognosis and the results to be exceptional.

Keywords: MCAM, Supply Chain Management, Risk factors

INTRODUCTION

Supply chain management involves the oversight and regulation of every step involved in the production of a product or the provision of a service. This encompasses all stages of the manufacturing process, starting from preparing the raw ingredients to delivering the finished product to the user. This include the finalization and transportation of the product as well. Implementing supply chain management systems may result in time and cost savings, as well as enhance the efficiency of the manufacturing cycle. Just-in-time supply chains, often known as

JIT, are now the prevailing practice in the industry [1]. The Just-In-Time (JIT) system enables the automated transmission of resupply orders for retail sales to the relevant producers. Subsequently, the goods may be replenished on the shelves with almost same speed to its removal and sale. An initial step towards enhancing this process may be analyzing the data given by the different partners to identify areas where further modifications can be made. Through the analysis of data provided by our partners, we have identified three specific occasions where efficient supply chain management positively impacts the whole supply chain cycle [2]:

The initial step is to discover potential concerns.

i. If a buyer buys more product than the manufacturer can provide, they may express dissatisfaction with the service quality. By utilizing data analysis, the producers have the potential to anticipate and eliminate any potential shortage, thereby avoiding any displeasure among consumers [1].

ii. Utilizing real-time data to get the most optimal price. The shelf life of seasonal commodities is sometimes reduced. These things are usually discarded or sold at significant markdowns when a season comes to an end. Dynamic pricing is commonly employed in businesses such as hotels and airlines, where the items being offered have a limited duration of availability, in order to effectively meet customer demand. Even for long-lasting products, the use of analytical tools and associated forecasting approaches can increase profits [3].

iii. a more equitable allocation of product inventory that is "available to promise." By utilizing analytical software tools, the work plan may incorporate the sales forecast, actual orders, and promised delivery of raw materials. These tools help in dynamically allocating resources and scheduling work. When the manufacturer provides an estimated delivery date for the products when the order is placed, there is a significant decrease in the number of orders that are filled incorrectly [4].

Methods to improve Supply chain

Improving supply chain effectiveness mostly involves focusing on the internal operations of the chain. Effective allocation of resources, be it financial, human, or physical, allows firms to meet consumer demand while minimizing expenses. The field of supply chain management extensively explores the benefits of customer responsiveness in terms of effectiveness and cost

efficiency. This illustrates that a strategy focused on meeting customer needs surpasses logistic supplier networks and just-in-time manufacturing in terms of outcomes. "Achieving optimal outcomes" might be considered as a substitute for organizational efficiency, which serves as a measure of internal effectiveness. Efficiency is an independent measure that may be used to evaluate an organization's performance in terms of its reliance on resources [5].

Efficiency is a valuable metric to use in a closed system where the amount of production is directly linked to the amount of profit. This system exhibits the typical features of machinery and bureaucracy. Examining activity networks like supply chains is more difficult than examining individual firms because of the increased flexibility of border situations, which makes it harder to obtain solid answers. Let's examine a dyadic system that operates efficiently based on its exchange value. The two parties evaluate the value of the deal by examining how the activity system utilizes its resources. Components such as a supply chain, an exchange system for the development and consumption of products, and a networking activity system may be found in an activity system. Efficiency may be attributed to a corporation that maximizes the utilization of all its resources. Nevertheless, due to the exorbitant expenses associated with inventory management, it is improbable that this could be executed in a system that combines production and consumption, such as a supply chain [6]. Supply chain efficiency assessments need meticulous deliberation of the objectives, hence employing both quantitative and qualitative methodologies for evaluation. The conceptual underpinning of efficiency forms the fundamental basis for the exchange value concept. The supply chain may be regarded as a quasi-organization due to its composition of many separate companies and an activity system. Interdependencies permeate the whole supply chain, overlapping and being shared. In the next part, we will discuss interconnection again, after trying to distinguish between effectiveness and efficiency as outcomes of the supply chain as an exchange system. For the trading system to commence, resources, also known as objects, are necessary. Consequently, the exchange unit is considered. The evaluation of the outcome considers both the object and the result [7].

Related works

One of the hazards in supply chain management is when a company fails to understand, anticipate, or interpret the potential changes in its environment, the potential consequences of these changes, and the feasibility of adjusting to them. Supply chain management includes the potential for hazards, such as the instability of enterprises and external factors that might cause changes. This vulnerability can result in unpredictable climatic conditions occurring at any point

in a worldwide supply chain. "[8]." Dynamic ecosystems can be influenced by several factors such as the availability of raw resources, client preferences, product demand, and technology. Due to the inherent unpredictability of environmental changes, it is imperative for businesses to be cognizant of these changes and respond accordingly. This is because these variables have an impact on a business's capacity to compete and shape its organizational and functional elements. Prior studies have classified uncertainty into three distinct categories: external uncertainties, internal supply chain uncertainties, and internal organization uncertainties, which are confined within the control of the focal enterprise. (Anomalies in the supply chain). The Jangga Team. "[8]". Supply chain flexibility, innovation, and environmental uncertainties are shown to be interconnected, as indicated by their research. The unpredictability of the environment is influenced by three factors: technical uncertainty, customer or demand uncertainty, and supplier uncertainty. Below, I will examine each unidentified environmental element individually.

Supply uncertainty refers to the level of variability and unpredictability in the performance of suppliers, specifically in terms of delivery and product quality [9]. Examples of supply uncertainty include the engineering prowess of the supplier, lead time, dependability of delivery, and product quality. These products, produced by the supplier, have the potential to impede or halt the production process. Moreover, these uncertainties will introduce unpredictability in the ordering process across the supply chain, resulting in surplus inventory, heightened transportation costs, and inefficient resource use. Even in a robust economy, a firm that is very attentive but receives subpar quality and delivery from its supplier may see a decline in customer service. This manufacturer is in risk of becoming extinct as a result of swift environmental changes.

Uncertainty in demand [2]: Consumer uncertainty refers to the extent to which a customer's preferences and needs exhibit irregular and unexpected behavior. The majority agrees that uncertainty, in general, is intensified by the unpredictability of demand. The competitive global market has led to customers' requirements for products and services becoming increasingly unpredictable and unclear in terms of volume, mix, time, and place, therefore impacting consumer choice. Modern clients have an increased expectation for a wider range of options, superior products, faster response times, and improved service.

The research categorizes the sub-factors of business management into three groups: innovations, process strategy, and marketing strategy. Business management (BM) involves the coordination,

strategic planning, and supervision of all relevant personnel and activities inside a firm in order to achieve goals and objectives. Businesses utilize process techniques to enhance production and market efficiency. To get perfection, it is vital to utilize the appropriate tools. The approach has been significantly influenced by decisions about distribution, promotion, and product-related marketing.

Technology uncertainty refers to the extent to which a sector is susceptible to change and lacks the ability to predict future technological improvements. Manufacturing and information technologies greatly improve supply chain integration and corporate operations, but they can pose threats to some companies. Investing in new technology might result in increased expenses for organizations due to the quick obsolescence of old technologies.

Qinghua [12] ran swiftly. Recently, there has been study conducted on supply chain management and sustainability. Supply chain sustainability involves organizations considering the impacts on both people and the environment across the whole production process, including sourcing raw materials, producing, storing, distributing goods, and any transportation-related activities. Consequently, a well-executed SSCM deployment enhances the company's operational and financial performance. This study examined food supply chain hazards from this perspective. The study used multivariate statistical analysis and structural equation modeling to elucidate the relationship between supply chain strategy (SCS), supply chain network design (SCND), organizational structure, information system, and the existing literature assessment. Based on the latest research, it has been shown that SSC (Shared Services Centers) significantly contribute to achieving both operational and financial success. This suggests that SSCM (Shared Services Center Management) should be seen as an extra strategy that has to be integrated into the overall company plan. The findings indicate that it is advisable to include SSCM into the company strategy and utilize it as a supplementary method. The authors interviewed 41 managers to gather their opinions on:

1. How can organizational planning and strategic communications be integrated?
2. The architecture of supply networks has a significant influence on the performance of enterprises.
3. What is the effect of SC's information system on performance?

The interviews are evaluated utilizing open-source, systematic, and narrative coding techniques. The researchers derived ideas for the questionnaire from interviews and published literature. The

initial version had two distinct sections: One survey collected demographic information from the participants, while another survey consisted of 46 questions. A panel of six experts from the SC sector and nine academic authorities conducted a thorough evaluation of the current draft in order to implement the required modifications.

Abdurrozzaq [13] proposed the use of normalization. Multiple approaches exist for assessing the overall effectiveness of the firm. The performance fulfillment rate is determined by the normalization of performance indicators. Each indicator's value is determined by a distinct scale. Normalizing is a crucial process that requires manipulating the equation of parameters. In order to ensure the reliability of performance measurement, it is essential to use normalization.

During this examination, the indication is transformed into a numerical range from zero to one hundred. The missing number is zero (0), while the largest number is 100. Consequently, the parameters for each indication are identical, resulting in an outcome that can be tested. Displayed below is a visual representation of a system used to monitor performance indicators. Process Analytical According to the concept of hierarchy. Thomas L. Saaty is the creator of the Analytical Hierarchy Process (MCDM) decision support paradigm. This decision-support paradigm utilizes a hierarchical structure to elucidate intricate scenarios that involve several criteria or components. One major benefit of the MCDM is its capacity to integrate both the objective and subjective elements of an issue. The building procedures for SCM instruments are described by Ebrahim [14]. These stages encompass large-scale data analysis, pilot research, pre-pilot study, and item development. In order to ensure the authenticity of the issue, most research studies incorporate comprehensive literature reviews as well as interviews with scholars and professionals.

A pilot study was conducted to evaluate the discriminant and convergent validity of the scale using the Q-sort method.

Performance measurement

Suppliers collaborate to create and implement supply chains that are highly efficient and cost-effective. Supply chain management, abbreviated as SCM, refers to this procedure. A project's supply chain encompasses the processes of production, product creation, and the requisite information systems for managing these activities. The primary goal of supply chain management is to establish connections between the production, transit, and ultimate delivery of

a product, or to exercise centralized authority over the whole supply chain. Efficient supply chain management allows organizations to save costs and expedite the delivery of items to clients. This is achieved by diligent monitoring of the company's inventory, as well as its manufacturing, distribution, and sales methods, together with the inventory of its suppliers [15].

In order to exceed client expectations, a corporation must effectively manage and allocate its resources. Once the supply chain is formed, it is important to create metrics to evaluate its effectiveness and efficiency, the benefits it provides to consumers, and its alignment with corporate objectives. [16]. Choose the enterprises that will provide you with the necessary resources to manufacture the goods. Subsequently, it is imperative to establish systematic procedures for overseeing and evaluating your associations with suppliers. The procedures of ordering, receiving shipments, maintaining stock levels, and authorizing vendor payments are all essential [15]. Develop a comprehensive strategy for procuring materials, manufacturing the product, conducting rigorous quality testing, packaging the product for shipping, and coordinating the delivery schedule [17].

It is crucial to handle client orders, coordinate freight and delivery schedules, invoice customers, and ensure timely collection of payments. The number 18 is enclosed in square brackets. When evaluating the efficacy of supply chain management (SCM), it is crucial to consider four essential factors: cost, quality, time, and flexibility. Our research indicates that several factors might potentially impact supply chain management. These components mostly comprise Several variables are taken into account, such as supply chain relationships (SCR), customer satisfaction (CS), manufacturing (M), business management (BM), information technology (IT), ecological uncertainty (EU), and supply chain management performance (SCP) [19]. Eleweet al.[20,21] devised a novel approach to tackle difficult problems by adapting the Firefly algorithm and implementing a scanning technique. The MC-GPSO technique was developed by Talib et al. in [22] and bin Hasnan et al. in [23] specifically for addressing large-scale challenges.

METHOD AND MATERIAL

The independent factors

In this study, we provide some conjectures that have been developed from evaluating the perceptions of several supply chain risk indicators and their impact on the relevance of risk

detection in supply chain management (SCM). This section also includes the justifications for the assumptions made by each part. In 2012, YING KEI delivered a presentation to the audience, covering the following key issues. The author's categorization of the probable sources of the supply chain problems he mentioned is as follows.

1. Operational risk
2. Inventory risk
3. Disruption risk
4. Quality risk
5. Technology risk

According to the expert, there are five variables that can independently determine the amount of risk posed by the supply chain in Iraq. Further analysis will be provided in the subsequent paragraphs.

MCDM Method

MCDA and MCDM, which abbreviate multi-criteria decision analysis and multi-criteria decision making, respectively, are utilized to generate decisions by taking into account several criteria. MCDA/MCDM techniques typically provide a finite number of choices, each characterized by a unique set of criteria. To assess each option, we may calculate several ratios that reflect distinct factors for choosing. By multiplying these ratios, it becomes possible to make comparisons. Every criterion is allocated a weight that is determined by its ratio. The WPM may be applied to solve any MCDA/MCDM problem, regardless of its dimension, whether it is one or two. For example, in situations when there are several options for making a decision that may be quantified using different units of measurement. One major advantage of this strategy is the use of relative values instead of absolute ones. The subsequent numerical example offers a clear and comprehensible depiction of the computations involved in this technique. We utilize the exact numerical values [24] for our dataset, which are derived from the same numerical occurrences in the weighted sum model.

$$W_j^- = \frac{w_j}{\sum_{j=1}^N w_j} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where } \sum_{j=1}^N w_j = 1$$

3. Calculate the preference value of every i -th alternative using formula 2.

$$S_i = \prod_{j=1}^N x_{ij}^{w_j^-} \quad (2)$$

Where the value of w is positive if the criteria is a benefit otherwise its value is negative.

4. Calculate relative preference value of each alternative to all alternatives using formula 3.

$$V_i = \frac{S_i}{\sum_{i=1}^M S_i} \quad (3)$$

5. The higher V value means the better the alternative.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The MCDM analysis can identify the predominant significant criterion and rank the indicators based on the responses provided by the participants. The subsequent sections include tables displaying the outcomes of the MCDM analysis for each criterion set. The ranking results provided insight into the significance of risks in evaluating supply chain management scenarios in relation to their possible consequences. The survey results from supply chain management revealed that the chosen criteria had a significant impact.

Table 1: the MCDM results factors

risk factor	rank
Operational risk	0.6429
Inventory risk	0.6181
Disruption risk	0.6333
Quality risk	0.6286
Technology risk	0.6095

Operational risk, with a score of 0.6429, is the most critical element in supply chain management. In order for the economy to sustain itself, it is essential that customers demonstrate a willingness to make purchases and that enterprises possess the capability to provide those demands. Consumer demand influences both interest rates and inflation, eventually resulting in increased output. Demand refers to the quantity of a product that buyers are willing and able to purchase at a certain price, whereas supply represents the quantity of the product that producers are willing and able to provide for sale. Price demand refers to the monetary value that buyers are prepared to allocate towards purchasing a product at a specific price point. Enterprises utilize this data to ascertain the optimal pricing strategy for a novel product. Consumers will make purchases based on their subjective evaluation of the things' worth. Price elasticity refers to the extent to which a change in price affects the demand for a product or service. If the reward is insufficient, the demand will be little or non-existent. In order to mitigate this risk, it is crucial that the pricing of the material equilibrium be precisely aligned with the purchasing power of the customer. The detail of risk effects shown in the figures below:

Figure 1: Operational risk results

Figure 2: Inventory risk results

Figure 3: Disruption risk results

Figure 4:Quality risk results

Figure 5: Technology risk results

The identification of operational hazards in a supply chain starts with a systematic examination of the process. It is necessary to thoroughly examine each step of the supply chain, including supplier selection and shipment tracking, in order to identify any weaknesses that might potentially cause problems. It is important to assess any external suppliers that may be engaged in the supply chain process to detect any vulnerabilities that might lead to cyberattacks or data breaches. Ultimately, it is crucial to evaluate the organization's technology and systems to see if they are adequate in meeting client requirements and mitigating losses caused by system malfunctions.

When hazards are identified during an examination of the supply chain process, as well as the third-party suppliers and technologies involved, it is crucial to promptly take action to reduce or eliminate them. To achieve this, it may be necessary to implement new processes that enhance both accuracy and security, such as doing a thorough review of each order before to shipment. Additionally, investing in state-of-the-art technology that is resistant to system failures and data breaches, such as a cutting-edge security architecture, may be advisable. It is important for companies to conduct frequent evaluations of their operations in order to identify potential vulnerabilities and implement necessary modifications based on consumer feedback or complaints.

Organizations must effectively handle operational risks to ensure uninterrupted and efficient service delivery. While operational risks are a natural aspect of any supply chain process, they may be efficiently identified and controlled through suitable solutions. Audit officers must have a thorough understanding of the sources of operational risk in a supply chain to guarantee compliance and protect their businesses from operational failures. Possible factors contributing to these issues may encompass communication breakdowns, inventory management mistakes, delayed shipping, instances of theft or fraudulent activities, cyber assaults, and compromised data security.

Conclusion

This article is to present a novel methodology for evaluating project risks in the context of supply chain management in Iraq. The objective is to develop a model that may assist those involved in food sales, distribution, and safety strategy. During the first phases of the project, it is important to identify potential impediments and hazards. In pursuit of that objective, the following acts were carried out:

1. In order to assess the impact of risk factors on supply chain initiatives, two surveys, expert interviews, and a meta-analysis of previous research were employed to identify the most influential variables. We have chosen five distinct kinds of supply chain management hazards.

2. The initial step in developing an MCDM model was selecting the appropriate application for the task. Microsoft Excel's user-friendly interface and analytical capabilities made it suitable for doing basic risk assessment. The MATLAB software was used to quantify the level of effect for each risk category.

The specialists deemed the risk prognosis and the results to be exceptional.

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